

Oxazine Dyes as Redox Indicators in Dichrometry*

N. VENKATESWARA RAO**, K. RADHAKRISNA MURTY† and (MRS.) C. KAMALA SASTRY

Chemistry Department, Andhra University, Waltair 530003

Manuscript received 27 May 1974; revised 13 January 1975; accepted 22 January 1975

The use of two oxazine dyes, Brilliant Cresyl Blue and Gallocyanine as redox indicators in the dichrometric titration of iron(II), hexacyanoferrate(II), uranium(IV), molybdenum(V), and hydroquinone in hydrochloric, sulphuric, phosphoric and perchloric acid media has been studied. Conditions for the satisfactory titrations employing these indicators have been established.

DURING recent times, Gowda and coworkers^{1,2} have reported the use of Chlorpromazine hydrochloride and Promethazine hydrochloride as redox indicators in vanadimetry. Puzanowska-Tarasiewicz³ has employed six phenothiazine derivatives, Chlorpromazine, Perphenazine, Thiopropazate, Promazine, Fluphenazine and Propericiazine as redox indicators in the determination of iron (II) by titration with ammonium vanadate. Muralikrishna⁴ has reported the use of Methylene Blue, a thiazine dye, as indicator in the titration of iron (II) with cerium (IV) ammonium nitrate, in perchloric acid medium, and this involves the oxidation of the normal form of the dye to a pink oxidised form. The present authors have recently reported the use of two oxazine dyes, Brilliant Cresyl Blue and Gallocyanine (Colour Index Nos. 51010 and 51030 respectively) as redox indicators in cerimetry⁵. In the present communication, we are presenting the results of our investigations on the use of these two dyes as redox indicators in the dichrometric titration of iron (II), hexacyanoferrate(II), uranium (IV), molybdenum (V) and hydroquinone in sulphuric, hydrochloric, perchloric and phosphoric acid media. The colour changes at the end points are very sharp and the results obtained are in very good agreement with those obtained by other methods.

Experimental

Reagents. All the reagents used were of reagent grade quality. 0.05*N* solution of potassium dichromate was prepared from B.D.H. AnalaR sample. 0.05*N* solutions of iron (II), hexacyanoferrate (II), uranium (IV), molybdenum (V), and hydroquinone were prepared and standardised.

Indicator solutions. 0.1% solutions of the dyes Brilliant Cresyl Blue (BCB) (E. Merck sample) and Gallocyanine (GC) (Chroma sample) were prepared

in doubly distilled water. We are grateful to M/S E. Merck, Darmstadt (Germany) for the gift of BCB. We have observed that the indicator action of the two dye solutions is retained for about 5-6 months.

From preliminary studies, we have found that the amounts of dye solutions required for producing perceptible colour changes at the end points, in a total volume of 50 ml, are : 0.5 ml of BCB and 0.2 ml of GC.

General Procedure

The following general procedure is recommended for the titrations : Treat an aliquot of the sample solution with enough 1 : 1 sulphuric, hydrochloric, perchloric or phosphoric acid, so as to give the required overall acidity, dilute to 50 ml, add 0.5 ml 0.1% BCB or 0.2 ml of 0.1% GC and titrate with 0.05*N* dichromate solution. The conditions of titration and the colour changes at the end points for the different reductant systems are given in Table I.

Indicator corrections. No indicator correction is necessary in titrations involving 0.05*N* solutions of potassium dichromate.

Transition Potentials. The transition potentials (vs. N.H.E.) for the titration of iron(II) with dichromate in the acid medium indicated are : Brilliant Cresyl Blue (in 4*N* sulphuric acid medium) : 790 ± 20 mV; Gallocyanine (in 1.0-3.0*N* perchloric acid medium) : 950 ± 10 mV.

Reverse titrations. The reverse titrations, i.e., titrations of dichromate with any of the above-mentioned reductants utilising BCB or GC as redox indicator, are not possible since these dyes are irreversibly oxidised in the presence of excess of dichromate.

Acknowledgement

We are grateful to the University Grants Commission for the award of a junior research fellowship to one of us (C.K.S.) and to the Principal, Mrs.

* Presented at the Annual Convention of Chemists held at Calcutta during December 23-30, 1973.

** To whom all correspondence may be addressed.

† Chemistry Department, Mrs. A. V. N. College, Visakhapatnam.

TABLE I—ACIDITY CONDITIONS AND COLOUR CHANGES AT THE END POINTS

Reductant	Indicator	Medium, colour change at the end point and sharpness of the end point			
		H ₂ SO ₄	H ₃ PO ₄	HClO ₄	HCl
Iron(II)	BCB	2.0–4.0 <i>N</i> ; turquoise green to violet; sharp end point.	3.0–5.0 <i>M</i> ; turquoise green to violet; sharp end point.	1.0–3.0 <i>N</i> ; light green to pink; sharp end point.	(a)
	GC	(a)	(a)	1.0–3.0 <i>N</i> ; light pink to light green; sharp end point.	(b)
Hexacyano-ferrate(II)	BCB	(a)	(a)	2.0–4.0 <i>N</i> ; deep green to yellowish green; sharp end point.	(b)
	GC	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a)
Uranium(IV)	BCB	6.0–8.0 <i>N</i> + 5–10 ml. of 1 <i>M</i> NaF solution; green to pink; sharp end point.	4.0–8.0 <i>M</i> ; green to pink; sharp end point.	4.0–8.0 <i>N</i> ; green to pink; sharp end point	3.0–6.0 <i>N</i> + 5–10 ml. of 1 <i>M</i> NaF solution + 7 ml of H ₃ PO ₄ ; green to violet to blue; sharp end point.
	GC	3.0–4.0 <i>N</i> + 3 ml of H ₃ PO ₄ ; light pink to light green; sharp end point.	(a)	(a)	3.0–4.0 <i>N</i> + 3 ml. of H ₃ PO ₄ ; light pink to light green; sharp end point.
Molybdenum(V)	BCB	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a)
	GC	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a)
Hydroquinone	BCB	(b)	(b)	(b)	(b)
	GC	0.5–2.0 <i>N</i> + 1.0 ml. of 1% potassium hexacyanoferrate(III); light pink to light green; sharp end point.	(b)	(a)	(a)

(a) Titration is not satisfactory.

(b) Titration is not possible.

A. V. N. College, Visakhapatnam and the authorities of the Andhra University, Waltair, for granting permission to one of us (K.R.K.M.) to carry out this work.

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